

Variable pay and job performance of shop-floor workers in lean production

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Abstract

Purpose- The study investigated design features of variable pay plans adopted for shop-floor workers engaged in manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production systems, and the effects of design features on their job performance.

Design/methodology/approach- 892 shop-floor workers attached to lean implemented manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka responded for the study. Structural equation modelling was used for the data analysis.

Findings- It was found that the performance evaluation-base for variable payments, variable pay calculation-base and goal setting for variable pay significantly predict job performance of the shop-floor workers.

Originality/value- It could be expected that the academics and practitioners alike are motivated by their desire to clearly apprehend the contribution of variable pay plans on job performance of the shop-floor workers engaged in lean production systems. This demands more investigations to better understand the design features of variable pay plans.

Key words lean production; job performance; remuneration; variable pay

Paper type Research paper

Introduction

The changes occurred in the global business environment made manufacturers world-wide to fundamentally change their production systems for survival and growth by moving away from low-discretion, control-focused work systems towards work systems that demand a higher level of participation of shop-floor workers, like lean production (Boxall and Macky, 2007; Godard, 2004; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995). These new work systems have a considerable effect on shop-floor workers since a greater autonomy and control are assigned to them over their job tasks and the methods of work (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Godard, 2004; MacDuffie, 1995).

Previous empirical studies imply that if organisations fail in the adoption of new technologies, the main cause tends to be human related issues rather than issues with their technical systems (e.g., Godard, 2004; Vidal, 2007). Consequently, there is a long tradition of interest in understanding mechanisms that can be used to make production jobs motivating and increase shop-floor worker involvement (Boxall and Macky, 2007; Haleem *et al.*, 2012; Libby and Thorne, 2009; MacDuffie, 1995). In this regard, some previous studies imply the importance of an appropriate pay system to compensate high pressure on shop-floor workers (e.g., Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995; Macky and Boxall, 2008; Snell and Dean, 1994). The present study investigates variable pay delivered to shop-floor workers in lean production in Sri Lanka.

A research on variable pay in the lean production can make important contributions to theory and practice. First, several previous research highlighted the importance of pay/remuneration in production settings with participatory work arrangements (such as Conti and Warner, 2002; Haleem *et al.*, 2012; Ichniowski and Shaw, 2003). However, the available few empirical studies on pay/remuneration in this context were several decades old (e.g., Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Snell and Dean, 1994). As a consequence, such studies do not provide sufficient information to make informed decisions on variable pay, as it is *actually* practiced in contemporary organisations that had implemented lean production systems.

Second, the research evidence for the effect of variable pay on employees is not conclusive (e.g., Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Jenkins *et al.*, 1998; Stone *et al.*, 2010; Wolf and Zwick 2008). Some studies provide evidence that variable pay plans increase individual effort and job involvement (e.g., Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Condly *et al.*, 2003; Rose and Manley, 2010; Sliwka, 2003; Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002). However, several other studies provide evidence that the variable pay plans fail to produce desired behaviour (e.g., Deci, 1972; Drake *et al.*, 2007;

Ganster *et al.*, 2011; Jenkins *et al.*, 1998; Wolf and Zwick, 2008) and create negative organisational outcomes such as decreased trust and cooperation (Christ *et al.*, 2008). However, we have not come across empirical studies that investigated the influence of variable pay on shop-floor workers in the lean production within the scope of our study. Consequently, more empirical studies are needed covering several organisations and different business sectors to understand which features of variable pay plans are attractive to make global conclusions.

In the above context, the present study investigates variable pay delivered to shop-floor workers engaged in manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production systems. The specific objectives of our study were to investigate a) design features of variable pay plans adopted for shop-floor workers, and b) effects of the design features of variable pay plans on their job performance. As variable pay presents an exciting area of research it is expected that an exploration of the linkages between these variables in the lean production would be of considerable interest worldwide, both theoretically and practically.

Review of literature

Human element and importance of remuneration in lean production

The reorganisation of manufacturing processes according to lean production requirements demands techno-organisational changes with a new strategy, structure, and the social organisation of work systems (Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park, 2006; Forza, 1996; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995). Therefore, a work system conducive to lean production should possess several core characteristics.

First, lean production demands team-based work organisation, where groups of shop-floor workers taking a high degree of responsibility for work within their areas (Åhlström and Karlsson, 1996; Bendell, 2005). Team-based work structures promote a fewer number of job classifications. As a result, tasks previously performed by indirect departments needs to be integrated into teams and this increases the work content of teams (de Treville and Antonakis, 2006; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Scherrer-Rathje *et al.*, 2009).

Second, in connection to the above, for the successful team task performance, teams should comprise of flexible, multi-skilled shop-floor workers (Åhlström and Karlsson, 1996; Bendell, 2005). Multi-skilled workforce increases flexibility and reduces the vulnerability of the production system (Forza, 1996). Therefore, task specific knowledge and skills of shop-floor workers should be maintained at very high levels.

Third, lean production requires an active job involvement of each shop-floor worker (Co *et al.*, 1998; Conti *et al.*, 2006; Olivella *et al.*, 2008). In a lean production setting, shop-floor workers' active job involvement manifests itself in many forms, such as the adaptation of work teams to variations in job duties in the production flow, the exchange of positions within the work group and the habit of "giving each other a hand" in moments of difficulty, and the commitment of each worker to the continuous improvement (de Treville and Antonakis, 2006; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Scherrer-Rathje *et al.*, 2009). For instance, in the context of lean production, Dahlgaard and Dahlgaard-Park (2006, p. 572) state:

"...lean production requires a culture where everybody is proactively working in reducing waste and in helping each partner. Everybody understands that his/her contribution is essential for the team in which he/she is a member. If he/she is not there – physically as well as mentally – there is a risk that the work will not be done as efficiently as possible. The success of the system depends on everybody's participation".

Therefore, high job involvement is an inherently desirable attribute of shop-floor workers in lean production, and each shop-floor worker needs to be highly involved in task performance.

Fourth, lean production requires participation of shop-floor workers in active shop-floor problem-solving that is central to *kaizen* (Forza, 1996; González-Benito, 2005; Olivella *et al.*, 2008). Employee participation in solving production problems and devising process improvements increase their job control (Lowin, 1968; Mulder, 1971). According to Forza (1996), shop-floor workers' participation is central to lean production and it is high in lean production plants than in traditional plants. The commitment of shop-floor workers for participation in decision-making is often accomplished through implementing schemes for suggestions, quality circles, and spontaneous problem solving (Forza, 1996; González-Benito, 2005).

Fifth, shop-floor workers should be provided with job autonomy to participate in root cause problem solving. Autonomy involves acting with a sense of volition and having the experience of choice that can be exerted over task performance (Gagné and Deci, 2005). Hackman and Oldham (1976, p. 258) specified autonomy as "the degree to which a job provides substantial freedom, independence and discretion to the individual in scheduling the work and in determining the procedures to be used in carrying it out". However, theoretical and empirical support for the existence of job autonomy in lean production is not definite (e.g., de Haan *et al.*, 2012; de Treville and Antonakis, 2006). De Treville and Antonakis (2006, p. 109) argue "individuals under lean production have almost no freedom,

independence or discretion in either how the work is scheduled (due to inventory reduction, short cycle times, and a flow-based layout) or the procedures to be used (due to process standardization). On the contrary, de Haan *et al.* (2012) argue that lean production emphasises creative tension, which challenges (instead of a burden) operators to creatively use their talents, skills and experience to identify waste and remove impediments to a job well done, thereby improving process control and output quality. Some studies provide evidence that adherence to operating procedures and the standardisation of work processes limit method control and impose restrictions on operators in the way job tasks should be performed (e.g., Angelis *et al.*, 2011; Conti *et al.*, 2006). However, some other studies provide evidence that operating procedures and the standardisation of work processes can have positive influence on job autonomy since these allow operators the right of self-government experiencing greater freedom from supervisory control, increased knowledge and self-discipline, increased worker self-efficacy beliefs and increased worker intrinsic motivation leading to output consistency in the context of repetitive manufacturing (refer to de Treville *et al.*, 2005). Further, some studies provide evidence to suggest that timing control experienced by operators in lean production is limited (e.g., Jackson and Mullarkey, 2000) while some other studies provide evidence to suggest that employees experience greater control for the pace of tasks (e.g., Mullarkey *et al.*, 1995). Furthermore, some studies provide evidence that employees hardly enjoy opportunities to realize autonomy to solve problems since the incidences of disturbances in lean production is very low (e.g., Schouteten and Benders, 2004).

Due to the above discussed inherent characteristics of lean production, shop-floor workers may experience lean work arrangements as burdens rather than challenges (MacDuffie, 1995; Macky and Boxall, 2008; Vidal, 2007). In this context, several previous research suggest the importance of properly designed remuneration system along with team work, performance monitoring and extensive training to ensure continued involvement of shop-floor workers in work processes, and encourage them to acquire new skills in planning, decision making and problem solving (Bhasin, 2008; Birdi *et al.*, 2008; Conti and Warner, 2002; Grove *et al.*, 2010; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Mund *et al.*, 2015; Olivella *et al.*, 2008). However, investigations on remuneration in the context of lean production or operations management are very rare to be found. Although Grove *et al.* (2010) identified the importance of incentives for target achievement they did not report how incentive system should be operated. Olivella *et al.* (2008) provide theoretical support for integrating wages to skills and performance but empirical support was not provided. Birdi *et al.* (2008) identified

the importance of empowerment, extensive training and team-based working as the components of human resource management (HRM) system in lean production overlooking remuneration. In a similar vein, when investigating people subsystem in lean production, Mund *et al.* (2015) did not take remuneration into account. Angelis *et al.* (2011) identified the importance of skill variety, responsible autonomy and work facilitation for workers to perform effectively in the lean production but overlooked the importance of pay or remuneration. Although Conti and Warner (2002) emphasised the importance of remuneration system, they investigated the existence of both individual performance pay and group performance pay at a very broad level. Our review of journals in popular databases of Business Source Premier, ABI/Inform, Emerald, ScienceDirect, Springer, Sage and Wiley failed to find any scholarly work since Karlsson and Åhlström (1995) to date that specifically investigated employee pay/remuneration in the context of lean production.

According to Karlsson and Åhlström (1995), if the remuneration system is not aligned with the work processes, organisations may not reward vital employee behaviour making the remuneration system an obstacle for the effective implementation of lean production. The literature suggests the importance of investigating fixed and variable pay components of any remuneration system that is designed for any context, including lean production (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Libby and Thorne, 2009; Peterson and Luthans, 2006). The fixed component or base-pay is the largest single component of the total remuneration package. Base-pay and annual increases to base-pay can very quickly trigger dissatisfaction whereas variable pay serves as a motivator (Risher, 2008). Variable pay contingent on performance enhances collective effort, professionalism and flexibility of shop-floor workers (Snell and Dean, 1994). Yet, the emphasis that should be given to variable pay component in a production system is not definite (Arthur, 1994; MacDuffie, 1995). Arthur (1994) specified a weak emphasis on the variable component for shop-floor workers while MacDuffie (1995) specified a strong emphasis. Therefore, an exploration of variable pay in the context of lean production would be able to provide valuable information for the advancement of knowledge and strategic decision-making.

Variable pay

Variable pay is the payment of cash to individuals in addition to the base-pay (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Peterson and Luthans, 2006). These payments do not become a part of base-pay and are not consolidated into the base-pay (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 273).

Therefore, variable pay recognises the performance of individuals or that of their team or organisation (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 274).

When delivering variable pay, a performance threshold or a base-line performance level needs to be established. This threshold is the minimum that must be reached by an employee or a group of employees in order to qualify for the payment (Snell and Bohlander, 2007). The key feature of variable pay is, it should be re-earned and employees have to accept the risk that they might not re-earn it (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 274). In other words, an individual risks not being receiving the payment again unless the same or a higher level of performance is achieved by reaching the targets assigned (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 274).

Variable pay constitutes of financial incentives (e.g., for each unit of output) and/or financial rewards (a lump sum spot bonus for a particular achievement) (Armstrong and Stephens, 2006; Peterson and Luthans, 2006). Financial incentives motivate employees to achieve assigned targets, improve their performance or enhance their skills by focusing on job priorities. For example, the “do this and you will get that” concept (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Armstrong and Stephens, 2006). Shop-floor payment-by-results plan is an example for such a payment (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 275). In contrast, financial rewards provide financial recognition to people for attaining their performance targets or reaching a certain level of skill (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001, p. 275). A lump sum spot payment for a particular achievement is an example for such a payment (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998; Peterson and Luthans, 2006). Overall, Armstrong and Murlis (2001, p. 274) identify financial incentives as forward looking while financial rewards as retrospective.

Our study is confined to investigate any type of variable pay, in the form of financial incentives or financial rewards that shop-floor workers in lean production are entitled to in addition to base-pay, and which are not consolidated into the base-pay.

Effects of variable pay on job performance

When building on the resource-based view of the firm, as an HRM practice, remuneration contributes to firm performance by leveraging on discretionary effort and desired knowledge, skills, attitudes and the behaviour of employees (Arthur, 1994; Barney and Wright, 1998). The argument behind this reasoning is that employees’ job performance is the direct outcome of how firms manage their workforce, which in turn may contribute to firm performance although the firm performance is not simply the aggregate of individual job performance

(Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Barney and Wright, 1998; Boxall and Macky, 2007). Theories such as social-cognitive, expectancy, agency, reinforcement and goal-setting are used predominantly to explain the effects of variable pay on effort direction, duration and the intensity of employees (Ganster *et al.*, 2011; Kumar and Vakkayil, 2011; Stone *et al.*, 2010). The basic rationale of variable pay plans is the simple proposition that employees are motivated by money to achieve job targets, improve performance or enhance their skills (Armstrong and Stephens, 2006).

Several previous studies provide evidence that well-designed and carefully implemented variable pay plans have dramatic positive impact on employees' job performance (e.g., Armstrong and Stephens, 2006; Condly *et al.*, 2003; Marsden, 2003; Rose and Manley, 2010; Sliwka, 2003; Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002). Marsden (2003) states that variable pay plans are used in many work contexts where direct supervision is problematic or expensive. Condly *et al.* (2003) identified that monetary incentives result in higher performance gains than non-monetary incentives. Sliwka (2003) and Rose and Manley (2010) argued that financial incentives could increase employee effort towards voluntary performance goals beyond minimum specifications. Stolovitch *et al.* (2002) found that incentives heighten employees' self-confidence, loyalty and increase the value assigned to work goals.

However, some previous studies suggest that variable pay fail to produce desired outcomes (Christ *et al.*, 2008; Deci, 1972; Drake *et al.*, 2007; Ganster *et al.*, 2011). Christ *et al.* (2008) provide evidence that variable pay decrease trust and cooperation. Drake *et al.* (2007) provide evidence that financial incentives lowered self-perceptions of competence and autonomy. Deci (1972) argued that incentives destroy personal interest in work. Ganster *et al.* (2011) suggest that variable pay triggers a stress-related cognitive appraisal process with implications for designing healthy workplaces.

The literature suggests the possibilities of using variable pay to compensate high pressure on shop-floor workers (e.g., Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995), generate discretionary effort (Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; MacDuffie, 1995) and lower voluntary turnover and job search behaviours (Snell and Dean, 1994). Further, variable pay increases workers' willingness to perform multiple tasks (Ichniowski and Shaw, 2003) and increases their effort-level irrespective of individual ability levels (Brüggen, 2011).

Given the importance of variable pay in lean production (e.g., Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995), it is of interest to understand the

design features under which the variable pay plans enhance job performance in lean production.

Design features of variable pay plans

The literature provides evidence for the importance of design features of variable pay plans to produce desired outcomes (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Lawler, 1971; Marsden, 2003). Lawler (1971) states that the design features have a strong motivational effect on employees if they value it, if they believe good performance is instrumental in bringing the desired reward and if they expect their efforts will achieve the desired performance. Any variable pay plan may fail if employees feel they lack scope to increase their effort, if they feel their effort make little difference to their performance, and if they believe that management lacks competence or good faith to evaluate and reward their performance fairly (Marsden, 2003). In such circumstances, employees may view variable pay plans as unfair and divisive (Marsden, 2003). In this regard, Ganster *et al.* (2011) state that how individuals are rewarded at work is perhaps one of the most salient features of the work environment, which serves as a source of satisfaction, challenge and fulfilment or a source of uncertainty, mistrust and perceived inequity.

Our rigorous review of academic journals failed to find previous studies that specifically investigated the effects of design features of variable pay plans or remuneration systems targeted at the shop-floor workers in lean production since 1996 to date. However, based on the available literature, following sections review the key design features of variable pay plans. These are namely, variable pay plan type, performance evaluation-base for variable payments, variable pay calculation-base and goal setting for variable pay. Where available, an attempt is made to link the available literature to the context of lean production.

Goal setting for variable pay. Goal setting plays an important role in flexible work environments, where employees' work effort is difficult to monitor through direct supervision (Marsden, 2003). The literature suggests the importance of the nature of goals set (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Marsden, 2003; Rose and Manley, 2010), employee participation in setting goals (Rose and Manley, 2010; Kumar and Vakkayil, 2011; Marsden, 2003) and mechanisms used for the assessment of goal achievement (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Rose and Manley, 2010; Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002) for the successful implementation and delivery of variable pay.

The literature suggests that properly constructed variable pay plans should have multiple goals covering different areas of task performance (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001;

Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Rose and Manley, 2010). According to Armstrong and Murlis (2001) and Karlsson and Åhlström (1995) goal setting is vital in the context of participatory work arrangements in just-in-time (JIT) and total quality management (TQM). Further, such goals should be specific, challenging and achievable, where the emphasis is on goal specificity and goal difficulty (Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002). According to Rose and Manley (2010), maintaining flexibility to modify goals and measurement process are also important.

Previous studies also provide evidence for the importance of non-managerial workers' participation together with line managers in formulating performance goals or learning goals reflecting work demands (e.g., Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998; Kumar and Vakkayil, 2011). The literature suggests that employees value variable pay to be tied to goal achievement (Marsden, 2003; Rose and Manley, 2010), and they tend to adopt such goals as of their own (Marsden, 2003). Studies of Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) and Marsden (2003) provide evidence for performance goals set in conjunction with workers and their supervisors that encouraged workers to achieve above average performance on a continuous basis.

Consistent with the majority of previous studies reviewed above, which indicates goal setting (for variable pay) enhances job performance (such as Marsden, 2003), and the importance of goal setting in the context of participatory work environments of JIT and TQM (e.g., Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995), it is hypothesised:

H1: Goal setting for variable pay has a significant positive effect on job performance in lean production.

Variable pay plan type. The literature distinguishes between individual plans and team plans (Condly *et al.*, 2003, Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998; Peterson and Luthans, 2006). According to Condly *et al.* (2003), individuals have more control over an outcome when it is more or less under individuals' control. Team plans are delivered to a team in the recognition of the achievement of team goals (Armstrong and Stephens, 2006; Peterson and Luthans, 2006).

Some previous studies compared the influence of individual and team plans on employee job performance (e.g., Condly *et al.*, 2003; Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Jones and Kato, 2012; Peterson and Luthans, 2006; Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002; Weisberg, 1996). Of these studies, Jones and Kato (2012), Peterson and Luthans (2006), Condly *et al.* (2003), Stolovitch *et al.* (2002) and Weisberg (1996) presented non-lean contexts while the studies of Karlsson and Åhlström (1995), Snell and Dean (1994) and Gomez-Mejia and Balkin (1992) presented advanced manufacturing contexts. Overall, above studies provided evidence that team plans had a markedly superior effect on performance compared to individual plans

(Condly *et al.*, 2003; Stolovitch *et al.*, 2002). Team plans promote an environment in which individuals' goals are intertwined (Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995), reward indirect labour that does not necessarily get noticed under individual plans (Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Weisberg, 1996), increase productivity (Peterson and Luthans, 2006) and promote horizontal monitoring within a team (Jones and Kato, 2012; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995).

However, some studies suggest the drawbacks of team plans (e.g., Ichniowski and Shaw, 2003; Jones and Kato, 2012). According to such studies, an individual may put in a considerable effort as a member of a team and yet may not realize any payment because of performance lapses on the part of team members, including free-rider behaviour and shortfalls in the mix of skills in the team (Condly *et al.*, 2003; Ichniowski and Shaw, 2003; Jones and Kato, 2012). If such issues in the design of the plan are not addressed properly, individual members may lose motivation to work harder (Jones and Kato, 2012; Peterson and Luthans, 2006; Snell and Dean, 1994; Weisberg, 1996).

Consistent with the majority of previous research reviewed above, which indicates that the plan type could influence the job performance (such as Condly *et al.*, 2003; Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Ichniowski and Shaw, 2003; Jones and Kato, 2012; Peterson and Luthans, 2006), and based on previous studies reviewed above, which suggests that the team plans may provide more benefits than the individual plans in the context of lean production (e.g., Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Snell and Dean, 1994), it is hypothesised:

H2: Variable pay plan type has a significant effect on job performance, where team plans have the highest effect compared to individual plans in lean production.

Performance evaluation-base for variable pay. The literature suggests that individual workers, the members of a team and teams participating in variable pay plans can potentially earn incentives if they meet pre-set performance goals (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Condly *et al.*, 2003; Libby and Thorn, 2009; Wageman, 1995). Specifically, variable pay can be delivered on the basis of meeting individual goals, team member goals, team goals or a combination of team member and team goals (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Condly *et al.*, 2003; Libby and Thorne, 2009; Wageman, 1995).

Individual goals are linked to performance at the level of each worker, for example, for each unit of output that meets targets, where he or she is an individual contributor and not a member of a team (Bonner *et al.*, 2000). In the achievement of numerous goals on

productivity, quality, timely deliveries and throughput times, shop-floor workers in multifunctional teams of lean production should engage in several job tasks involving planning, purchasing, materials handling and continuous improvement. Therefore, Karlsson and Åhlström (1995) state that individual goals (e.g., on number of pieces produced) are inappropriate and the appropriate remuneration system should take into consideration the whole process.

Team member goals evaluate each team member's contribution and outcomes when distributing variable pay. For example, the extent to which a team member meets his/her goals that further the team's overall performance (Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998). Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) state that this type of assessment is inappropriate for full-time teams where job tasks are interdependent and substantial cooperation among team members is desirable. The operations management literature suggests less feasibility and less desirability in making payments on the basis of team member goal achievement (e.g., Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Snell and Dean, 1994).

Team goals evaluate each team's contributions and outcomes when distributing variable pay, i.e., the extent to which the team meets assigned goals (Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998; Snell and Dean, 1994). When the team meets assigned goals, each and every team member earns predetermined payment (Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998). Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) argue that team goals are effective only if the organisation has full-time teams where tasks are interdependent and substantial cooperation among team members is desirable.

The literature also provides evidence for the use of mixed structures. For example, a combination of team member goals and team goals (Libby and Thorne, 2009; Locke and Latham, 1990; Wageman, 1995). In other words, the variable pay plan has both team member goals and collective goals. Some researchers such as Locke and Latham (1990) provide evidence that the mixed structures decrease free-riding in the team. However, Libby and Thorne (2009) provide evidence that mixed structures send confusing signals to team members about where to direct their effort, causing team members to experience goal conflict. Wageman (1995) argued that when team members have to focus on the team member as well as team tasks in mixed structures, they may find difficulties in developing collective processes in team production environments.

Consistent with the majority of previous studies, which suggest that the performance evaluation-base for variable pay could influence job performance (such as Bonner *et al.* 2000,

Libby and Thorne 2009), and based on the previous studies reviewed above, which suggest that the meeting team targets could provide more benefits in the context of lean production than any other alternative performance evaluation-bases (e.g., Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995), it is hypothesised:

H3: Performance evaluation-base has a significant effect on job performance, where meeting team member targets and team targets have the highest effect of all performance evaluation-bases in lean production.

Variable pay calculation-base. The management literature provides evidence for different mechanisms used in the calculation of variable pay (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Ganster *et al.*, 2011; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995). Some previous studies provide evidence for the calculation of variable pay on individual piece-rate basis for each unit of output that meets or exceeds targets (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Ganster *et al.*, 2011; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Snell and Dean, 1992). However, since piece-rate encourages individuals producing as many units as possible Karlsson and Åhlström (1995) concluded that it is not appropriate for lean production, which emphasises an integrated process. Snell and Dean (1992) state that firms with flexible technology and manufacturing practices may require variable pay plans that motivate employees to acquire new skills and provide flexibility to apply these skills in a timely way. This also implies inappropriateness of delivering variable pay on individual piece-rate basis.

Some previous studies provide evidence for rewarding employees on the basis of flat-rate, where a fixed amount of money is paid for the time spent in performing the task (Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Rydval and Ortmann, 2004). Hence, flat-rate does not link pay to goal achievement either on overall basis or individual unit of output basis (Bonner *et al.*, 2000).

Some previous studies provide evidence for alternative mechanisms used in calculating variable pay in the team work environment (e.g., Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998; Steiner, 1972; Weisberg 1996). Weisberg (1996) provides evidence for the payment on the basis of performance of the average performer in the team. Steiner (1972) provides evidence for the payment on the basis of performance of either the highest performer or the lowest performer in the team. Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) provide evidence for paying a percentage of base-pay for each team member for meeting or exceeding goals (e.g., 10% of base-pay). Hoffman and Rogelberg (1998) further state that even though all team members were assigned the same percentage of base-pay, the payment received by each member varies since all of them are not on the same base-pay. However, we have not come across empirical

evidence for the calculation of variable pay of shop-floor workers as a percentage of monthly base-pay.

Armstrong and Murlis (2001, p. 340-342) provide evidence for the use of lump sum spot bonus payments (financial rewards) in the context of TQM and JIT for meeting targets. According to Armstrong and Murlis (2001), a lump sum bonus was paid in the context of TQM for achieving targets such as zero defects, producing prime quality products, decrease in the percentage of output rejected and an increase in the percentage of deliveries made on time. Armstrong and Murlis (2001) also provide evidence for bonus payments in the context of JIT for achieving targets of inventory, work-in-progress and set-up times.

Consistent with the previous studies reviewed above, which suggest that the variable pay calculation-base could influence job performance (such as Bonner *et al.*, 2000; Hoffman and Rogelberg, 1998), pay calculation based on piece-rate is not appropriate for the context of lean production (e.g., Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; Snell and Dean, 1992) and shop-floor workers in TQM and JIT were delivered bonus payments for achieving performance targets (Armstrong and Murlis, 2001), it is hypothesised:

H4: Variable pay calculation-base has a significant effect on job performance, where making a lump sum bonus payment has the highest effect of all calculation-bases in lean production.

Methodology

Population and Sample

Our target population for the study is a cross section of individuals engaged full-time in export-oriented manufacturing firms in Sri Lanka. The following criteria were set in selecting the firms belonging to the study population. 1) A firm should be registered under the Board of Investment of Sri Lanka (BOI) since it is compulsory that all BOI registered firms should export at least 90 per cent of their output. 2) A firm should have implemented a formal lean production system in the whole manufacturing function and it should be the standard of operation for at least one year. This restriction will isolate firms that had achieved good progress in lean statistics such as work in progress (WIP), first time through (FTT), efficiency of the process, delivery in full on time (DIFOT), accepted quality level (AQL) and cut ship. 3) Following Shah and Ward (2003), firms with more than 100 employees were selected. We identified 14 firms that fulfilled the criteria set for the study, which belonging to the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) 22 and 23 (22 -Textile mill products, 23 - Apparel and other

finished products made from fabrics and similar materials). All these firms agreed to participate in the survey.

With regard to the characteristics of the responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1993 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2004. The ownership of all the firms lay with locals. All the firms have adopted lean production methods after 2005, where the latest adoption occurred in two of the firms in the year 2010. On average, these firms had achieved good progress in the implementation of lean with WIP of 35 days, FTT of 70%, efficiency of the process of 90%, DIFOT of 85%, AQL of 91% and cut ship of 90%. When the firm size is measured in terms of average annual turnover and the number of people employed, the respondent firms had an average annual turnover (in US\$) ranging from 80 to 400 Million while the total number of employees ranged from 300 to 5000. All the firms had a dedicated section to handle lean implementation headed by a senior level manager.

To fulfil the expectations of the study, 1200 self-administered survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 5% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. A total of 922 responses were received; 892 usable responses resulted in a 74% response rate. With regard to the characteristics of shop-floor workers responded, 59% had 10 years of schooling while 41% had 13 years of schooling. 24% of the respondents were male while 76% of the respondents were female. Mean age was 25 years (S.D. = 5.10, median = 25), the mean number of shop-floor workers in the lowest formal work unit (team/section) was 61 (S.D. = 20, median = 36), mean job position tenure was three and half years (S.D. = 3.04, median = 3) and mean tenure with the present employer was three years and four months (S.D. = 2.96, median = 2.5). All shop-floor workers received their variable pay entitlements together with their monthly wage, which is paid to them not earlier than 25th day of a given month and not later than 10th day of the following month fulfilling labour regulations of the country.

Measures

Variable pay plan type was measured by two items on a nominal scale, i.e., individual and team. Performance evaluation-base for variable pay was measured by four items on a nominal scale, i.e., meeting individual goals, team member goals, team goals and a combination of team member and team goals. Variable pay calculation-base was measured by four items on a nominal scale, i.e., percentage of base-pay, piece rate, lump sum bonus and flat rate. For each of the three constructs, a tick box labelled “other” was added to enable respondents to state

any other design features that are practiced in his/her firm, which was not offered by the questionnaire.

Goal setting for variable pay was measured by the six-item scale developed for the study based on the insight gained from the literature reviewed above. The items were on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 “Strongly Disagree” to 5 “Strongly Agree” where higher scores indicate a higher level of practice in goal setting for variable pay.

Job performance was measured by the six-item scale developed for the study based on the insight gained from the literature reviewed above. The items were on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 “Strongly Disagree” to 5 “Strongly Agree” where higher scores indicate a higher level of task accomplishment.

Respondents’ age, gender, tenure in the job position and the number of shop-floor workers in the lowest formal work unit (team/section) were also inquired in the questionnaire. Respondents’ age, tenure and the number of shop-floor workers in the lowest formal work unit were assessed by the natural logarithmic transformation of the values provided by the respondents for each construct.

Methods of data collection and analysis

The self-administered survey questionnaire was in two parts. Part one inquired about shop-floor workers’ perceptions towards goal setting for variable pay, job performance and demographic data. After responding to these questions, workers were instructed to handover each questionnaire to their immediate supervisors to complete the part two of the questionnaire. The part two of the questionnaire was on variable pay plan type, performance evaluation-base for variable payments and variable pay calculation-base. Each shop-floor worker’s immediate supervisor responded to these three design features by indicating to which design features each worker belongs to. For example, for a particular worker, the immediate supervisor may identify team-based as the variable pay plan type, meeting team goals as the performance evaluation-base and the percentage of base-pay as the calculation base by selecting one response from each nominal scale. We followed this mechanism of data collection to avoid shop-floor workers providing fictitious information if they are not 100% accurate in their variable pay entitlements. Hence, we distributed the questionnaires to shop-floor workers and collected the completed questionnaires from supervisors. Participants including both shop-floor workers and their supervisors were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and ensured the confidentiality of their responses. After the completion of data collection via questionnaire, we interviewed few randomly

selected supervisors from each firm to obtain more details of the nature of variable pay plans. These interviews were conducted to corroborate the findings of the questionnaire survey.

Responses for the two variables (i.e., job performance and goal setting for variable pay) on Likert scales were mean centred to increase interpretability of the relationships. For these two constructs, Cronbach's alpha reliability of measurement scales were examined and principal components factor analysis (varimax rotation) was conducted. In doing so, we adhered to the criteria of eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7. Convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) while discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE.

Descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and path analysis were used to test the hypothesised relationships. For the path analysis, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS.

Results and discussion

Design features of variable pay plans

Table 1 shows means and standard deviations for the item measures of goal setting for variable pay.

Table 1

The validity and reliability of this measure were evaluated. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Table 3 shows the breakdown of respondents by variable pay plan type, performance evaluation-base for variable pay and variable pay calculation-base. As can be seen in Table 3, the majority of respondents belonging to team plans, where variable pay was delivered

subjected to meeting team member and team targets, and variable pay was calculated based on each unit of efficiency and lump sum bonuses.

Table 3

To obtain a detailed picture of the design features of variable pay plans, we interviewed randomly selected unit managers attached to production plants of the firms. All most all firms practiced a similar type of variable pay plans. But we were able to identify few differences in the design features used by textile and apparel manufacturing firms; few differences in the design features used for shop-floor workers attached to quality departments and shop-floor workers attached to all other production departments of apparel manufacturing firms.

First, shop-floor workers in apparel manufacturing firms could be broadly classified into two groups, namely, the shop-floor workers attached to quality departments (minority group) and the shop-floor workers attached to all other production departments (majority group). The majority was on team plans. Their performance was evaluated for variable pay on the basis of both team member targets and team targets. The *team member target* was the attendance. In this regard, the industry experiences a high absenteeism rate and a monthly average turnover rate of 8% for shop-floor workers in textile and apparel manufacturing firms (Department of Census and Statistics n.d.a). Hence, firms use incentives to mitigate this major labour issue in Sri Lanka. Shop-floor workers were delivered a lump sum bonus for attendance, for instance, Rs. 2000.00 (in Sri Lankan Rupees) was paid if all the work days were present, Rs. 1750.00 if one day was absent and Rs. 1500.00 if two days were absent for a particular month. However, workers who were absent beyond two days were not provided with this bonus. When it comes to *team targets*, two types of targets were given, namely, financial incentives for efficiency targets and lump sum bonus for team attendance targets. In detail, first, each team was given efficiency targets depending on the number of days a particular export order will take to complete. For instance, day 2 efficiency target was higher than day 1 target. All team members of the teams, which exceed efficiency targets were delivered financial incentives. For instance Rs. 50.00 was given for each unit of efficiency. Although we understood that there are differences between each firm in their method of calculating efficiency ratios, the firms refused to provide the key performance indicators they used in calculating efficiency ratios. Second, team attendance bonus (lump sum bonus in flat-

rate) was paid only if all members of the team were present on a particular month, where no one was absent on a single working day of the month. Overall, shop-floor workers entitled to team member attendance bonus, team attendance bonus and team financial incentive calculated based on each unit of efficiency at the end of a particular month as variable pay, in addition to fixed base-pay. Further, although the variable payment amounts varied from one firm to another, the concept of payment is the same across the firms.

In contrast, shop-floor workers attached to quality departments of apparel manufacturing firms were identified as individual contributors; they were on individual plans. They received a payment on flat-rate at the end of the month for their involvement in performing the job tasks. In addition, they received a monthly lump sum bonus for attendance, where the method of calculation was the same as discussed above. Although the amounts paid varied from one firm to another the concept of payment was the same across the firms. Overall, our interviews revealed that the firms had some concern over flat-rate payment designed for these workers. They identified that the designated flat-rate was not very successful in attracting, retaining or motivating these workers for their job tasks.

Second, all shop-floor workers in textile manufacturing firms were on team plans. Their performance evaluation for variable pay is on team member targets and team targets. As discussed earlier, the team member target is the attendance. They were provided with the lump sum attendance bonus as detailed above. With regard to team target, since items produced are textiles or bundles of clothing, the whole production line or plant was working as a team. Once the export order was completed, depending on the quality of the product a quality incentive was paid as a percentage of base-pay, if the final product was rated as a prime quality product.

Job performance

Table 4 shows means and standard deviations for the item measures of job performance with variable pay plans.

Table 4

The validity and reliability of this measure were evaluated. The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5

Design features of variable pay plans and job performance

Zero-order correlations are shown in Table 6. As detailed in the section on measures, our dependent variable was on Likert scale. Of the four independent variables, three were on nominal scales while one was on Likert scale (i.e., goal setting for variable pay). Of the variables that were on nominal scale, variable pay plan type was coded as “individual plan” = 0 and “team plan” = 1; performance evaluation-base for variable payments was coded as “for the time spent in performing job tasks” = 0 and “meeting or exceeding team member and team targets” = 1. Variable pay calculation-base had three response categories as shown in the Table 1. Hence, this variable was dummy coded for the multiple regression analysis. In doing so, two dichotomous dummy variables were created (i.e., number of response categories minus 1) for response categories “percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus” (D1) and “unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus” (D2) while treating the response category “flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus” as the reference category. The results of multiple regression were interpreted by comparing each of the two categories to the reference category. Each dummy variable was coded as "1" for the cases in its assigned category, and "0" for all other cases following the recommended statistical guidelines (Stacks, n.d, Stockburger, n.d.). As can be seen in Table 6, correlations between independent variables are low suggesting low collinearity, whereas correlations between three independent variables (performance evaluation-base, calculation-base and goal setting for variable pay) and the dependent variable are high, suggesting better prediction in the regression analysis.

Table 6

In the first stage of SEM, shop-floor workers’ age, gender, tenure in the job position, and the number of shop-floor workers in the team/unit were entered into the model. Since none of these variables were significant, in the process of purifying the SEM model, these variables were subsequently removed (Kremelberg, 2011). In the second stage of the analysis the main

variables were entered. The inclusion of main independent variables into the model resulted in achieving a good level of fit having $\chi^2/df = 4.82$, GFI = 0.84, CFI = 0.89, and RMSEA=0.04. The summary of analysis is provided in Table 7.

Table 7

As can be seen in Table 7, goal setting for variable pay, variable pay calculation-base and performance evaluation-base for variable payments were significant in predicting job performance. Squared multiple correlation of 0.587 suggests that these three variables account for 58% of the variation of job performance. Specifically, goal setting for financial incentives had a significant positive effect on job performance. This supports H1. Variable pay plan type was not significant in predicting job performance. Hence, H2 was not supported by the data. H3 predicted that performance evaluation-base will have a significant effect on job performance, where meeting team member targets and team targets have the highest effect of all performance evaluation-bases. As can be seen in Table 7, performance evaluation-base had a significant positive effect on job performance. Independent sample t-test was carried out to identify which evaluation-base is significant, namely meeting or exceeding team member and team targets or time spent in performing job tasks. The results are shown in Table 8. As can be seen in Table 8, the job performance of workers who were on “meeting or exceeding team members and team targets” is higher than those who were on “flat-rate payment for the time spent in performing job tasks”, and the difference is significant. Hence, H3 was supported by the data.

Table 8

Hypothesis 4 predicted that variable pay calculation-base will have a significant effect on job performance, where making a lump sum bonus payment has the highest effect of all calculation-bases. As can be seen in Table 7, variable pay calculation-base is significant in predicting job performance. Both D1 and D2 were significant in predicting job performance. Therefore, the results suggest that variable pay calculation-base add significantly to the

prediction of job performance. Specifically, whether shop-floor workers belong to either “flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus” versus “percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus” or “flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus” versus “unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus” add significantly to the prediction. ANOVA was conducted to isolate the effect of each response category. The results are shown in Table 9. Further analysis of least significant differences (LSD) revealed that workers on “unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus” were more likely to yield a higher level of job performance than workers on “flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus”. Further, workers on “percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus” were more likely to yield a higher level of job performance than workers on “flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus”. Furthermore, the difference between “unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus” and “percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus” was also significant suggesting that the calculation-base of “unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus” yields the highest job performance. Overall, the results of the study support H4 where variable pay calculation-base has a significant effect on job performance, and lump sum bonus payment is the calculation-base that had the highest effect of all calculation-bases.

Table 9

Conclusions and implications

Although the operations management literature emphasises the importance of remuneration system in attracting, retaining and motivating employees, empirical studies in this area is not abundant. It is even very rare to find empirical research that investigated effects of pay on employees in the context of lean production. The present study investigated the design features of variable pay plans directed to shop-floor workers in the lean production environment. Building on the available literature, four key design features of variable pay plans were investigated, namely, variable pay plan type, performance evaluation-base for variable payments, variable pay calculation-base and goal setting for variable pay.

The findings suggest that the majority of shop-floor workers in the lean production environment were on team plans, and they were assigned both team member targets and collaborative team targets. This finding supports previous studies that emphasised the importance of having team based remuneration systems in the context of lean production

(e.g., Armstrong and Murlis, 2001; Conti and Warner, 2002; Grove et al., 2010; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995;). It was revealed that firms deliver variable pay in terms of team member targets as well as team targets to mitigate issues with absenteeism in lean production. In the unit-based production system prevailed in the apparel firms, team targets were based on efficiency achievements by the team. In contrast, in the quality-based production system prevailed in textile firms, team targets were based on the quality of the final textile product. In this regard, Armstrong and Murlis (2001) also provide evidence for the delivery of variable pay for achieving targets such as zero defects, producing prime quality products and decrease in the percentage of output rejected in the context of JIT and TQM. We also found that efficiency ratio is the main calculation-base for variable pay in the apparel firms while a percentage of base-pay is the main calculation-base for variable pay in the textile firms.

We further observed apparel firms having dedicated quality departments to ensure the quality of items produced, and shop-floor workers attached to these departments were delivered a lump sum payment on the basis of flat-rate, where a fixed amount of money is paid for the time spent in performing the task. However, this payment does not link pay to target accomplishment at either team or individual level, which is a main drawback. Previous studies of Bonner *et al.* (2000) and Rydval and Ortmann (2004) also provide evidence for the existence of such payment systems in their studies. However, these two previous studies were not conducted in the context of lean production or operations management; we have not found any study conducted in the lean production context for direct comparison.

The findings also suggest the prevalence of setting goals for the purpose of variable pay. We inquired several areas of goal setting such as the nature of goals set, time provided to achieve goals, the communication of goals and the involvement of shop-floor workers in setting/changing goals (refer to Table 2 for item measures). Several previous studies also emphasised the importance of knowing employee perceptions and reactions towards variable pay in terms of communication of information (Sweins *et al.*, 2009), fairness and equity (Cox, 2005), employees' understanding of how variable pay aligns with overall objectives of the work (Rose and Manley, 2010) and employees' participation in the design of variable pay plans (Jenkins and Lawler, 1981). However, these previous studies are not conducted in the context of lean production or operations management.

The operations management literature emphasises that the variable pay can be used as an inducement to encourage workers to acquire new skills in planning, decision making and problem solving (e.g., Appelbaum *et al.*, 2000; Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995; MacDuffie, 1995; Macky and Boxall, 2008; Snell and Dean, 1994). This is critical since increase in effort

may not translate into improved task performance unless individuals possess required capabilities to perform the tasks. However, we have not come across the design features of variable pay plans that address acquiring/enhancing workers' capabilities in our study.

The main intention of the study was to investigate the effects of design features of variable pay on job performance of shop-floor workers in the context of lean production. Armstrong and Murlis (2001) in the context of JIT and TQM provided evidence that well-designed variable pay plans increase plant level productivity. The findings of our study suggest that the design features of performance evaluation-base, calculation-base and goal setting for variable pay significantly predict job performance. It was revealed that performance evaluation-base of "meeting or exceeding team member and team targets" had the highest effect on job performance. Further, when the extent of goal setting for variable pay is higher job performance increases suggesting a positive relationship. The variable pay calculation-base of "unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus" had the highest effect on job performance while "flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus" had the least effect. Overall, the findings suggest that variable pay plans tied to employees' achievements create a lean production environment that recognises shared commitment where every shop-floor worker contributes to desired outcomes.

The findings of our study have important implications for the theory and practice. With regard to the contribution of the study for the literature on lean production/operations management, as stated earlier, few studies had investigated remuneration systems in the operations management literature (e.g., Gomez-Mejia and Balkin, 1992; Snell and Dean, 1994) and very few studies had investigated variable pay systems in the context of lean production (e.g., Karlsson and Åhlström, 1995) and these studies were several decades old. In this context we have provided new data on variable pay as it is *actually* practiced in contemporary organisations that had implemented lean production. Therefore, we believe that the present study made a contribution to the literature by providing information on variable pay as it is actually practiced in a sample of manufacturing firms that had implemented lean production. However, we were unable to find previous studies conducted in the context of lean production or any other management setting to make a comparison. Yet, it is expected that the findings of the study will provide academics and practitioners with new insights into design features of variable pay that influence job performance in the context of lean production, and will be a source of general guidance in stimulating more in-depth future research in this area.

With regard to the contribution of the study for practice, the management literature, in general (e.g. Peterson and Luthans, 2006), suggests that variable pay-for-performance outcomes may have a high instrumental value in putting extra effort worthwhile. The findings of our study imply the importance of designing variable pay to influence specific behaviours and desired production outcomes in lean production. Specifically, findings imply the importance of selecting performance evaluation-bases and calculation-bases for variable pay and goal setting for variable pay. When capturing and capitalising on individual capabilities, there is a need to better understand design features that are effective in fulfilling expectations of lean production as well as workers employed in those. Therefore, the findings of our study suggest that variable pay is an important aspect that should be aligned with the demands of lean production.

Finally, it should be noted that this research was designed as a cross-sectional study employing survey methodology. Being a small island nation, the number of manufacturing firms operating in Sri Lanka with more than 100 employees is less than 1500 (Department of Census and Statistics of Sri Lanka n.d.a), and the number of firms that had implemented lean production is even smaller. It may be possible to find substantial differences in the incidence of variable pay across firms in similar industries, substantial within-firm heterogeneity concerning the distribution of a particular variable payment among employees and substantial within-establishment heterogeneity in employee knowledge of the coverage of variable pay. Therefore, future research in different and large samples and longitudinal studies are necessary complementing with questionnaire surveys and interviews. Although we concentrated only on variable pay plans, our preliminary investigation revealed the practices of delivering non-monetary rewards to shop-floor workers, such as achievement awards. Hence, future studies could broaden the scope by investigating total remuneration package directed to shop-floor workers in the context of lean production. Further, future research could take into account the nature of tasks being performed and the impact of variable pay on different work tasks in lean production.

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Tables

Table 1. Design features of variable pay - goal setting for variable pay

	Mean	S.D.
Management considers employees' ideas to amend the scheme	3.35	.96
Goals set by the scheme are clear and specific	3.62	.94
Goals set by the scheme are challenging but achievable	3.69	.90
Goals set by the scheme are relevant to my job profile	3.83	.85
Time period given to achieve the work goals are fair	3.52	.92
Overall mean	3.6	.73

Table 2. Validity and reliability - goal setting for variable pay

	Factor loading	AVE	Construct reliability	Square root of AVE	Cronbach's alpha
Management considers employees' ideas to amend the scheme	.728	.541	.855	.736	.84
Goals set by the scheme are clear and specific	.714				
Goals set by the scheme are challenging but achievable	.722				
Goals set by the scheme are relevant to my job profile	.712				
Time period given to achieve the work goals are fair	.798				

Table 3. Design features of variable pay - plan type, performance evaluation-base, and calculation-base

	Frequency	%
Variable pay plan type:		
Team plan	722	80.9
Individual plan	170	19.1
Performance evaluation-base for variable payments:		
Meeting or exceeding team member and team targets	722	80.9
For the time spent in performing job tasks	170	19.1
Variable pay calculation-base:		
Unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus	612	68.6
Flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus	162	18.2
Percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus	118	13.2

n = 892

Table 4: Job performance

	Mean	S.D.
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me more aware of the importance of being sensitive to my colleagues	3.83	.79
Performance based financial incentive scheme has been an inducement for me to get my work priorities right	3.80	.84
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me to show more initiative in my job	3.66	.91
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me to improve the quality of my work	3.83	.84
Performance based incentive scheme has been an inducement for me to fulfill the requirements of the job correctly	3.86	.85
Performance based incentive scheme means good work is rewarded	3.78	.88
Overall mean	3.79	.67

Table 5. Validity and reliability – job performance

	Factor loading	AVE	Construct reliability	Square root of AVE	Cronbach's alpha
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me more aware of the importance of being sensitive to my colleagues	.758	.583	.893	.763	.87
Performance based financial incentive scheme has been an inducement for me to get my work priorities right	.733				
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me to show more initiative in my job	.759				
Performance based financial incentive scheme has made me to improve the quality of my work	.803				
Performance based incentive scheme has been an inducement for me to fulfill the requirements of the job correctly	.740				
Performance based incentive scheme means good work is rewarded	.787				

Table 6. Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1 Age	1								
2 Gender [†]	.083	1							
3 Job position tenure	.381**	.055	1						
4 Shop-floor workers in the team/unit	.121	.066	.126	1					
5 Performance evaluation-base [‡]	.017	.046	.006	-.038	1				
6 Calculation-base – D1	.067	.026	.007	.082	.239	1			
7 Calculation-base – D2	.048	.035	.009	.045	.238	.073	1		
8 Variable pay plan type [‡]	.074	-.023	-.104*	.029	.161**	.187	.113	1	
9 Goal setting for variable pay	.044	.202**	-.066	.129	-.126**	.130	.061	-.048	1
10 Job performance	.095	.019	.033	.080	.277**	.281**	.268**	.035	.696**

Note: *p<0.05; **p<0.01, † binary coded.

Table 7. Summary of results: structural model coefficients

Path	Standardized regression estimate	Squared multiple correlation
Goal setting for variable pay ---> Job performance	.691***	.587
Calculation-base – D1 ---> Job performance	.389***	
Calculation-base – D2 ---> Job performance	.276**	
Performance evaluation-base ---> Job performance	.254**	
Variable pay plan type ---> Job performance	.107	

Notes: *** p<.001, ** p<.01

Table 8. Results of t-test - differences in job performance by performance evaluation-base

	Job performance		t
	Mean	S.D.	
Performance evaluation-base for variable pay:			3.831***
Meeting or exceeding team member and team targets	3.87	.62	
For the time spent in performing job tasks	3.66	.71	

Note: n = 892; ***p<0.001

Table 9. Results of ANOVA - differences in job performance by variable pay calculation-base

	Job performance		F
	Mean	S.D.	
Variable pay calculation-base:			7.371***
Unit of efficiency and lump sum attendance bonus	3.99	.65	
Flat-rate and lump sum attendance bonus	3.11	.62	
Percentage of base pay and lump sum attendance bonus	3.53	.67	